

Risk Management in Higher Educational Institutions: A study of Mehran UET, Jamshoro, Sindh (Pakistan)

Author's Details:

Sonia Memon¹, Dr Abdul Sami Qureshi¹, Dr Asif Ali Shah², Dr Adnan Pitafi², Mehtab Abbasi² Abdul Ghani Abbasi²

Abstract

Nowadays, the risk management is attracting a lot of attention in academia, business, management and other corporate world. The idea, basically, is to address potential hazards in an orderly, systematic fashion, and to devise mitigation strategies for dealing with these unfortunate events - well before they actually occur. Risk management conducted in order to reduce the impact of potential hazards within Mehran University to an acceptable level. This paper first introduces the concepts of risk management and then presents some of the more apparent internal and external issues\ risks associated with the processes needed to create and implement a system of quality management based on the ISO 9001:2015 standards within Mehran University of Engineering and Technology Jamshoro, Sindh. The questionnaire has been developed in accordance to ISO 9001: 2015 parameter and consulted by (QEC) of Mehran University of Engineering & Technology, Jamshoro Sindh. For qualitative approach, total 17 questionnaires have been distributed each among Academic as well as Non-Academic department of Mehran University Jamshoro. Further, data was then analyzed through manifest content analysis to investigate the findings. The study identified several internal and external issues related to academic and non-academic institutes of Mehran University Jamshoro. According to the results, several risk factors have been identified such as shortage of employees, need of career development, faculty training, lack of machineries and equipment, courses delivery online, lack of skilled lab staff and lack of communication between academic and industries. Nevertheless, results portrays a clear picture of university departments where availability of resources were lacked in and requires early response strategy. Internal issues such as Machineries and Equipment is on extreme level risk that is catastrophic and infrastructure is a major risk factor identified in the research study. In conclusion, (HEIs) Higher Education Institutes should envisage comprehensive plans to address risk management issues in universities. This

research will help in assessing the risk functioning in parallel with the implementation of system through effective mechanism to ensure better quality performance regarding quality management and standard activities in university arena.

Keywords: ISO 9001:2015, Risk Management, Quality Management System, Higher Education Institutions

I. INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT

Risk assessment is a term used to describe the overall process or method to identify the hazards and risk factors that cause potential harm. It is a process of identifying, assessing and controlling threats to an organization's capital and earnings. These threats, or risks, could stem from a wide variety of sources, including financial uncertainty, legal liabilities, strategic management errors, accidents and natural disasters. The word "risk" means that uncertainty can be expressed through probability. The risk is a probabilistic event that can exist and affect the activity of an organization a positive opportunity or negatively hazards (Bakr et al., 2012).

Nowadays, the risk assessment is an important research theme because the risk always present in the industrial as well as educational institution activities Olsson R., (2007). Veland and Ave (2013) proposed the same based classification of risk given by Aven (2008) and they used theses definition to discuss how the risk perspectives influence the risk communication between the decision-makers, the risk analysts, experts and lay people. Indeed, for Karimiazari *et al.*, (2011), engineers, designers and contactors view risk from the technological perspective, lenders and developers tend to view it from the economic and financial side. So, the question is: what is a risk? The first answer, the risk is the probability that an event or action may adversely affect the organization. For Mazouni (2011), the risk is an intrinsic property of any decision, it is measured by a combination of several factors (severity,

occurrence, exposure to, etc.), although it is generally limited to two factors: severity and frequency of occurrence of potentially damaging accidents that incorporate some exposure factor. Besides, as a result, a risk management plan increasingly includes companies' processes for identifying and controlling threats to its digital assets, including proprietary corporate data, a customer's personally identifiable information (PII) and intellectual property. However, every business and organization faces the risk of unexpected, harmful events that can cost the company money or cause it to permanently close. Risk management allows organizations attempt to prepare for the unexpected by minimizing risks and extra costs before they occur.

Abraham (2013) pointed out that many higher education institutions are recognizing that an effective risk management program, with the full support of the governing board will increase a university likelihood of achieving its plans, increase transparency, and allow better allocation of scarce resources. Good risk management is good governance Abraham (2013, p.5). Besides, overall risk management helps a university to sustain its competitive advantage, solidify its integrity and reputation, respond effectively when a significant event occurs, avoid financial surprises and effectively manage all of its resources.

(HEI) Higher education institutions are facing internal and external challenges within the institutions. However, higher education institutes faced with a complex network of educational providers in a competitive global environment and this gives rise to 'strategic' risks, exemplified by the challenge of maintaining staff- student ratios at levels that provide not only an acceptable quality of a student learning experience with relevant educational activities but also are dependent on an adequate supply of research infrastructure for addressing research requirements.

Risk management is the piece of the university culture and is incorporated into the strategic planning process and objectives of each department. Individual departments and divisions at the university recognized what their risks are, will take responsibility for managing those risks, and will assess their performance in managing their risks. Therefore, the departments are taking

the responsibility for managing their risks through their strategic planning process and are holding themselves responsible for their risk management performance in risk management (Clyde-Smith, 2014).

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Risk Management is a fundamental issue for various organizations, when we discuss the risks involved in day to day operations we find that many of us are vulnerable as we fail to identify and take preventive measures. Therefore, identifying the internal and external risks associated with the processes is required for implementation of various systems of quality management based on the ISO 9001:2015 standards. Higher Education in the scope of ISO has only recently added Risk as one of the key factors that need to be identified, assessed and mitigated in order to the smooth functioning of tertiary level education.

III. RESEARCH QUESTION

The study is conducted to research the following question:

What kind of risks is being faced by Mehran University of Engineering and Technology in optimizing its human resource performance?

IV. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To identify the activities at departmental level and evaluate the elements associated with risk.
- To assess the risks and measure their severity and chances of occurrence at departmental/institutional level in reference to the quality management based on the ISO 9001:2015.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW:

A. RISK MANAGEMENT

Emily J. Stebbins-Wheelock and Al Turgeon (2018) argued that process of assessment of risk and monitoring of risk management is at center of organizational risk management. By the increasing this process whole organization, look the both "positive aspect" and "negative aspect" risk,

Primarily, risk management is the process of making and implementing decisions that will decrease the poor effect of inadvertent losses on an organization as defined by (Baranoff,

Harrington, & Niehaus, 2005). Risk portrayed as “any potential problem that threatens the accomplishment of a project” (Taylor, 2006). Besides, risk management has moved from quantitative methods to composed risk management forms with the end goal of comprehension and embedding risk management all through the task's life cycle (Artto, 1997). PRINCE2® (2009) defined as a doubtful event or set of uncertain event that, should it happen, will affect the accomplishment of goals. A risk is estimated by a blend of the likelihood of an apparent risk or opportunity happening and the level of its effect on targets. However, describing as an improbable event or set of unsure event that, should it happen, will impact the accomplishment of goals. A risk is evaluated by a mix of the probability of an obvious hazard or opportunity occurring and the dimension of its impact on targets.

Risk assessments are being utilized in probation to decide an individual's component of risk to complete another new wrongdoing, along these lines deciding the judgment of supervision that individual have to get subject to provide evidence based practices (DeMichele and Payne, 2010). Risk evaluation is a fundamental and very significant procedure to make sure the organization resources and status against security threats and risk. It gives a visibly identifiable image of the present threats that the organization is confronting and encourages the top management to take the correct decision to wipe out or mitigate those risks ISO 9001 is a global Standard of (QMS). This Standard demonstrates the necessities for organizations to permit them to progress continual upgrades and achieve consumer loyalty (Sari, Wibisons, Wahyudi, & Lio, 2017). Current example in wellbeing region and the zone of Quality of management (for instance ISO 9001:2015) are situated on pointed for the planning, which keep the disaster by successful and fruitful tools (Pačaiová, 2017). A risk evaluation and management procedure is usually used to verify an organization's advantages and the organization itself from being a casualty of attacks develop unidentified risk. Moreover, risk assessment encourages the organization to get a clearly certain image of the present safety condition, identify the risks that are confronting the organization, and the required controls to mitigate these risks, assessed

misfortunes and the effect on case the risk has been used. (Shaker, Nagy, Raafat, and Abuzaid, 2012).

(Lichtenstein, 1996) explained risk assessment approach that is used to finish a risk assessment for an organization's information security. Nowadays, there are many risk assessment approaches from which to pick, each showing an arrangement of issues. However, risk assessment can be portrayed: The assurance of quantitative or qualitative value of risk identified with a strong situation and a known threat (Stonebumer, Goguen, and Feringa, 2002). It is fundamental to receive criteria that may be use and evaluating the importance of risk. The criteria rely on the various situation and requirement. Besides, the main criteria should be measure in the organizational risk management policies and ought to be characterized in the begun of the development, similarly as, looked out for at continuously (Ruzic-Dimitrijevic & Dakic, 2014). (Sum & Saad, 2017) explained regarding risk management in perspective of university is consistently access to a small city. University risk managers face the demoralizing challenge of identifying and dealing the complex risks over their campuses. Fortunately universities have lower loss rates than the industrial sector. However, the expenditure of claims to higher education institutions both financially and from a public image point of view can be imperative. Risk management is the piece of the university culture and is incorporated into the strategic planning process and objectives of each department. Individual departments and divisions at the university will recognize what their risks are, will take responsibility for managing those risks, and will assess their performance in managing their risks. Therefore, the departments are taking the responsibility for managing their risks through their strategic planning process and are holding themselves responsible for their risk management performance in risk management (Clyde-Smith, 2014).

Cassidy et al. (2001) defined five kinds of risks faced by universities. (i) Strategic Risk (ii) Financial Risk (iii) Operational Risk (iv) Compliance Risk and (v) Reputation Risk. (Abraham, 2013) pointed out that many higher education institution foundations are recognizing that an effective risk management program, with the full help of the administering board will

improve a university probability of accomplishing its plans, increase clarity, and agree to better allocation of limited resources.

The risk assessment methodology is the same in all regions, and it ought to include the following steps:

- i. Introduction to the structure (organization and action), work process, establishment, apparatuses, and so on,
- ii. Recognizing the risk that can be harmful for the system
- iii. Risk will be assessed in relation to harm and risk
- iv. Ways and measures for the risk reduction, mitigation and eradication should be decided
- v. Re-evaluation of risk, with respect to the leftover dangers and damages (after directed elimination) and took measures for sustaining the lasting level of risk.

B. ISO 9001 STANDARD

During 1970s the requirement for requesting of a variety of national quality standards on a worldwide scale showed up. The organization recognized work for this purpose (International Organization for Standardization) directed to improvements in 1987 the first version of ISO 9000 series standards updated in 1994 and 2000.

Requirements concerning a management system of quality of and organization that demonstrate the client's demand satisfying ability are referred by ISO 9004:2000, and 2008. Solution for the requirement exceeding basic criteria of ISO 9001 standard is proposed in ISO 9004:2000 standard, moreover it also highlight the ways for development of overarching quality management system.

(Jodkowski, 2015) proposed Requirements concerning the 9001:2008 QMS submit to eight groups of issues: 1. focus on clients, 2. leadership, 3. worker involvement, 4. process approach, 5. system approach to management, 6. continuous improvement, 7. fact-based approach to decision making, 8. mutually beneficial relationship with providers. According to (Deysner 2014) ISO 9001 included, as a matter of course, the idea of risk management, along with these lines the 2015 version of the standard is progressively express and incorporating this concept into the management system. (Fonseca & Domingues

2017) have highlighted the ISO 9001 standard, involved by the Technical Commit of the International Standardization Organization (ISO/TC 176), characterizes requirements to help organizations on the quality and agreement of their products and services, satisfying client's necessities. (Sitnikov, Bocean, Berceanu, & Pirvu, 2017) suggested that, Concerning the ISO 9001:2015 standard, not all the processes of the quality management system contain the similar amount of risks which affect the capacity of an organization to fulfill its objectives (ISO, 2015). Similarly, the case of some organizations, the consequences of producing goods and services which are not in accordance with standards can determine only nonessential inconveniences for the client. In the case of other organizations, the outcomes can be far more prominent and have a sweeping effect. In this context; "risk-based thinking" offers the possibility of choosing the degree of planning and control of the quality management system.

C. HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INTUITIONS

Kezar (2001) expressed that the situation in which HEIs work is remarkable and essentially not the same as private industry, requiring the advancement of new ideas and procedures for authoritative change. In his study regarding higher educational institutions, he proceeds with neglecting the diverse logical components found in advanced education causes disappointments in investigation and methodology, the association's capacity to connect with the partners expected to impact change. URMIA, (2007) noticed that HEIs work in an intricate and changing condition made out of societal, monetary, and advertise powers. HEIs are additionally compelled to change their business practices.

VI. METHODOLOGY

The main objective revolves around assessment of Risk Management in (HEI) Higher Education Institutions. Identification of activities at departmental level and elements associated with it and assessment of risks inside the university premises. To achieve this, both qualitative and quantitative approaches has been employed to observe results through brief analysis of research objectives. Primary data has been collected through an open-ended and close-ended questionnaire from Teaching and Non-Teaching

staff of Mehran University of Engineering & Technology, Jamshoro.

Figure 1: Research Flowchart

A. SAMPLE

The sample and audience that we surveyed belong to Academic and Non-Academic of Mehran University of Engineering and Technology, Jamshoro Sindh Pakistan. Among academic and Non-Academic staff 16 and 13 Sectional Head were selected for obtaining their viewpoint regarding the research study. Moreover, age of respondents were 45-50 years were 44% and above 50 years were 54%. Among all respondents, only one female participated in the survey research and all were male respondents.

B. DATA COLLECTION

For conducting of this research study, questionnaires were designed for collecting data from Sectional Head of Departments of Mehran University Jamshoro. Convenience sampling technique was used to target population. The format of questionnaire was designed from different questionnaires of previous researches, and then developed after review of literature and as per the objectives of proposed research study. Moreover, 18 questionnaires (open-ended) and 16 (close-ended) questionnaires were distributed among the departmental head for obtaining their view point. Only 16 (close-ended questionnaires) and 13 (open-ended questionnaires) were received back fully filled. Besides, manifest content analysis was used to analyze qualitative data and mean statistics were observed through (SPSS) Statistical Package for Social Sciences to evaluate quantitative data analysis to depict the results.

VII. RESULTS & FINDINGS

A. DISCUSSION

The data reveals the fact that objectives of study were analyzed through Manifest Content Analysis techniques. The discussion will highlight key objectives of proposed study and more importantly data collected from several departments of Mehran University of Engineering & Technology, Jamshoro regarding risk management in (HEIs) Higher Education Institutions that will help in observing results.

This study aimed to investigate the risk management in (HEIs) Higher Education Institutes: Mehran University of Engineering & Technology, Jamshoro Sindh, Pakistan. The analysis focus on primary data and is a qualitative approach. However, this research study consist of two objectives related to identifying and measuring and mitigation of risks at university. This study used Manifest Content Analysis method to evaluate and analyze data and conclude research study objectives.

The study observed that (HEIs) Higher Education Institutions must be responsive to the challenges of the rapidly changing and challenging new world: expectation of society and growing demands of the rising student population. Besides, several HEIs) there are many types of internal issues that are faced by higher education institutions. On the other hand, this study also identifies several internal issues faced by academic side of Mehran University. Machineries and equipment, infrastructure, faculty training, shortage of faculty, admission intake, teaching aid, skilled lab staff, non-teaching staff training, building maintenance, course delivery online, shortage of stationary, research lab, admission intake, fire, data center building structure, power redundancy, internet, lack of advance technology and transport issue etc.

In addition to this, 13 departments of Mehran University Jamshoro Sindh Pakistan provided data regarding Risk Management internal as well external risks. Sum, Md, (2017) also pointed out risks faced by University of Malaysia in every facet of its existence. Besides, the risks are grouped into institutional areas. The followings presented the risks: emergency alert systems for natural disaster, competition for faculty, faculty governance issues, grants, human subject, animal, and clinical research, intellectual property, internship programs, joint programs/partnerships, laboratory safety, online learning, plagiarism,

quality of academic programs, student records, unions and workplace safety, building and renovation, fire, infrastructure damage, off-site programs, public-private partnerships, residence hall and apartment safety. Thus, data results showed clear picture of risks attached with university arena where identification of risks demand envisaging new strategies for mitigation of risks from (HEIs) Higher Educational Institutions.

Several universities also manage and response these risks through university-based mitigation strategies. However, study highlighted most repeated issues were identified and repeated at Mehran University Jamshoro Sindh Pakistan which were harmful or risky for the university. Highest risks indicated by the institutes were Machineries & Equipment, infrastructure and Teaching faculty that have possible chance of occurrences. Additionally, some departments pointed out that high, job market, communication gap, COVID-19 pandemic and electricity were identified highest risks factors and contribute severe occurrence of chances in the risk indicated by departments of Mehran University Jamshoro Sindh Pakistan.

This study also highlighted shortage of Teaching Faculty, Need of Design Development Center, Lack of Latest Technology, Shortage of Teaching Assistant and Supporting Staff were identified in various academic departments. However, Risk Assessment Matrix used to draw and check which issue is critical and risky for departments at Mehran University.

Finally, the study showed that academic and non-academic departments of Mehran University Jamshoro face number of issues inside the departments. There is a very positive view regarding the early resolution of issues academically and administratively. However, from the above results, it is concluded that in order to resolve risk mitigation (HEIs) Higher Education Institutions should take comprehensive measures to control and mitigate risk in a bid to save university from future severe risks.

OBJECTIVE # 1: TO IDENTIFY THE INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL ISSUES AT DEPARTMENTAL/INSTITUTIONAL LEVEL AND EVALUATE THE ELEMENTS ASSOCIATED WITH RISK.

A. INTERNAL ISSUES

Figure 1: Internal Issues

Figure 1 shows internal issues at academic departments of Mehran University Jamshoro. Most of the respondents pointed out various internal and external issues related to the risks to the risk in Mehran University of Engineering & Technology, Jamshoro.

Result revealed that 24% of the departments are facing machineries and equipment issue, and 16% facing infrastructure issue, 11% facing the issue of faculty training, meanwhile 8% facing shortage of faculty.

B. EXTERNAL ISSUES

Figure 2: External Issues

Figure 2 shows external issues at academic departments of Mehran University Jamshoro. However, most of the respondents highlighted external issues such as Engineer Job Market 27%, communication gap between department and industry 21% Covid-19 pandemic & Electricity 14% were by some departments of Mehran University Jamshoro. Thus, issues highlighted by

the respondents showed maximum attention of authorities concerned.

OBJECTIVE # 2: TO ASSESS THE RISKS AND MEASURE THEIR SEVERITY AND CHANCES OF OCCURRENCE THROUGH THE RISK ASSESSMENT MATRIX AT DEPARTMENTAL/INSTITUTIONAL LEVEL IN REFERENCE TO THE QUALITY MANAGEMENT BASED ON THE ISO 9001:2015.

Issues Identified		Maximum Reasonable Consequences				
		Insignificant (1)	Minor (2)	Moderate (3)	Major (4)	Catastrophic (5)
		Skilled lab staff	Shortage of faculty	Faculty training	Infrastructure	Machineries & equipment
Likelihood Rating	Almost Certain (5)	Medium 5	High 10	Extreme 15	Extreme 20	Extreme 25
	Likely (4)	Low 4	High 8	High 12	Extreme 16	Extreme 20
	Possible (3)	Low 3	Medium 6	High 9	High 12	Extreme 15
	Unlikely (2)	Low 2	Low 4	Medium 6	High 8	High 10
	Rare (1)	Low 1	Low 2	Low 3	Low 4	Medium 5

Figure 3: Risk Assessment Matrix (Internal Issues at HEIs)

Figure 3 shows that Risk Assessment Matrix was prepared after identification of issues at Mehran University Jamshoro. The issues identified were compared with High, Medium and Low Risk Ratings. However, the results shows that several departments expressed that there was highest risks are attached with each department and some of them have extreme level of high risk that could have severe chances of occurrences.

In addition to this, data suggests that internal issues such as University Machineries &

Equipment is one of the Catastrophic Risk available in various departments of Mehran University and several departments are facing same kind of issues because various university departments were facing similar issues. Moreover, Infrastructure at university departments is the major high risk is highlighted by the institutes. On the other hand, shortage of faculty facing issue of shortage of teaching staff identified as minor level risk and Skilled Lab Staff is also internal issue but it is Insignificant. The finding shows that there are several internal problems attached with each department at Mehran University Jamshoro and need swift consideration of issues and its resolution from authorities concerned for mitigation of internal possible risks. Thus, future risks can only be mitigated when we have such plans to strategically handle issues academically and administratively with full participation from (HEIs) Higher Education Institutions.

Issues Identified		Maximum Reasonable Consequences				
		Insignificant (1)	Minor (2)	Moderate (3)	Major (4)	Catastrophic (5)
		contractor coordination	Delay in response from HEC	Electricity	Linkage between academic & industry	Engineer job market
Likelihood Rating	Almost Certain (5)	Medium 5	High 10	Extreme 15	Extreme 20	Extreme 25
	Likely (4)	Low 4	High 8	High 12	Extreme 16	Extreme 20
	Possible (3)	Low 3	Medium 6	High 9	High 12	Extreme 15
	Unlikely (2)	Low 2	Low 4	Medium 6	High 8	High 10
	Rare (1)	Low 1	Low 2	Low 3	Low 4	Medium 5

Figure 4: Risk Assessment Matrix (Internal Issues at HEIs)

Figure 4 represents Risk Assessment Matrix that signifies issue at university level was how much

severe and critical. The risk assessment matrix was prepared after identification of issues at Mehran University Jamshoro. The issues identified were compared with High, Medium and Low Risk Ratings. However, the results shows that several departments expressed that there was highest risks are attached with each department and some of them have extreme level of high risk that could have severe chances of occurrences.

In addition to this, data suggests that external issues such as Engineer Job Market is one of the Catastrophic Risk available in various departments of Mehran University and several departments are facing same kind of issues because various university departments were facing similar issues. Moreover, Linkage between Academic and Industry is the major high risk is highlighted by the institutes. Although, one of the most important problem of electricity was identified as Minor Level of Risk. Availability of electricity and other alternatives were need of the university to cope with the problems being faced by the students and faculty staff. On the other hand, Contractor Coordination is also external issue but it is Insignificant. The finding elaborates several internal problems attached with each department at Mehran University Jamshoro and need attention of relevant authorities for early resolution of issues and for mitigation of internal possible risks. Thus, future risks can only be mitigated when we have such plans to strategically handle issues through full support from (HEIs) Higher Education Institutions i.e. Mehran University Jamshoro.

A. QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF ACADEMIC INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL ISSUES

The respondents were asked through open-ended questions on Risk Management at academic side. According to them, they highlighted that the departments were facing numerous issues at departmental level. According to their viewpoint, university's academic departments were facing several internal issues. In addition to this, the departments have highest number of previous students and every years new batch comprised of thousands of students join different undergraduate, post-graduation and PhD studies. Normally, every year university manage issues as per the detection of university's department but have no any active plan available.

This study identifies issues at university remains a high demand shortage of faculty, supporting and recruitment of new (TAs) Teaching Assistant, Latest Technology, Linkage of Academia and Industry and Need of New Design Centre at various departments of post-graduation studies. Nowadays, (HEIs) Higher Education Institutions lacks in various financial and administrative problems. There is a greater need of early resolution of issues of university departments with full support of (HEIs) Higher Education Institutions and areas identified must be handled without further delay to save time, machinery and equipment of university.

B. QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF NON-ACADEMIC INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL ISSUES

The respondents were asked through open-ended questions on internal and external issues of Risk Management at non-academic side of Mehran University Jamshoro. According to their opinion, most of respondents expressed the view that university lacks in several facilities and required to improve and manage it. However, some respondents viewed that lack of financial support for officers, issue of internet and power failure faced by administration department of university, delay of response from (HEC) Higher Education Commission and lack of understanding among faculty and administration staff. In addition to this, internet and power failure raise more serious risks that prevail in the department and power failure obviously restrict flow of communication. That's why the issues highlighted full severe issues during survey of data. This resulted possible risk occurrences and university administration requires to take steps in highlighting issues soon after the detection so that mitigation plan could have successful consequences. Also, some respondents viewed that in normal circumstances, the administrative affairs are running smoothly.

However, data reveals that internal issues highlighted by the Non-Academic departments' shows several issues that have possible chances of risk occurrences. According to their viewpoint, they pointed out several internal issues that department of administration faced and highlighted most possible risks. Most of respondents viewed that lack of financial support of employees, (SOPs) Standard Operating Procedures, lack of clerical staff, lack of water

facility for officers/officials, infrastructure equipment, fire extinguishers, shortage of furniture/infrastructure, staff training and retention and technological update of software were the issues of administration department of Mehran University. They observed that the related issues were lacked in and need urgent delivery and quick resolution so that management can cope with. Thus, it is very important for (HEIs) Higher Education Institutions to envisage a comprehensive plan for early resolution of internal and external issues of university as per the perspective of ISO-9001-2015 within the tertiary educational institute i.e. Mehran University Jamshoro.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The qualitative analysis of research study comprehensively concludes the most important points of topics analyzed and discussed based on research objectives. The study aimed to investigate the risk management in (HEIs) Higher Education Institutes: Mehran University of Engineering & Technology, Jamshoro Sindh Pakistan. The analysis focuses on primary data, collected from various departments of Mehran University Jamshoro to respond research issues from primary sources. In addition, Manifest Content Analysis has been conducted and comprehensive brief analysis has been used for data processing. The research consists of one research question consist of: How to identify, manage and mitigate the internal & external issues at departments of Mehran University and two research objectives?.

The findings of this paper shows that identification of several Internal and External issues faced by Mehran University have been identified. This portrays a clear picture of university departments where availability of resources, communication gap, infrastructure, faculty training, shortage of faculty, teaching aid, skilled lab staff, internet and light issues, machineries and equipment were essentially requires an early response strategies from quarters concerned etc. Normally, university departments face every day new issues and respondents highlighted issues that were requirement of university departments. However, 17 open-ended questionnaires were distributed each among various academic and non-academic departments of Mehran University Jamshoro, of them (76%)

questionnaires were returned from respondents fully filled. On the other hand, 17 questionnaires were distributed among non-academic department where we received (100%) response from respondents.

In second objective, risk assessment matrix was prepared to measure possible risk chances of university departments. First, issues were identified and then issues were measured through the severity and chances of occurrences by using 5x5 risk rating scale e.g. extreme, high, medium and low. The study concluded that the internal issue of machineries and equipment is on extreme level risk and the issue of infrastructure is on major high risk that is facing by departments of MUET Jamshoro. Moreover, the external issue of Engineer Job Market is on extreme level risk and the Communication Gap between Academia and Industry is on major high level risk.

In addition to this, it further concludes that the internal issue of machineries and equipment is on extreme level risk that is catastrophic and the issue of infrastructure is on major high risk that is facing by departments of MUET Jamshoro. Moreover, the external issue of Engineer Job Market is on extreme level risk and the communication gap between academia and industry is on major high level risk.

Further, certain risks cannot be directly linked to the financial aspect of an organization and their mitigation strategies should be able to be shared within academia and the industry. Thus, an assessment and response strategies should be understood by controlling the outcome of the risk event should further be included in the identification, assessment and response of new risk events.

Also, certain risks cannot be directly linked to the financial aspect of an organization and their mitigation strategies should be able to be shared within the industry and academia. Assessment and response strategies should be understood by controlling the outcome of the risk event should further be included in the identification, assessment and response of new risk events.

Similarly, organizations should promote risk mitigation plans to implement better process control by a second or third opinion on the risk assessment and risk response preferably as an iterative measure such as risk management

process should be. (HIEs) Higher Educational Institutes should implement structured risk management workshops within their organizations to better identify, analyze, respond to and control risk.

Further, more experienced individuals should focus on and be more involved in the risk identification stage. Through their experience, more risks would be identified and therefore they can be assessed, responded to and controlled. However, the risk propensity of the individuals seemed to be consistent even with increasing years of experience.

This will further enhance the social sustainability within the organizations and the industry where each opinion will be equally important. Also, by incorporating more experienced individuals as well as less experienced individuals, or moderators, to effectively question the assessment of risks and therefore mitigating the shift in reference point for risk perception.

Moreover, top management utilizes an approach that is more proactive instead of reactive following the potential outcome of the risk event would further emphasize a better outcome control. This since risk management practitioners will be more inclined to assess risks accordingly. Also, by utilizing a better control of outcomes and the process leading up to that outcome, lessons learned can be spread within the organization.

Therefore, internal and external issues highlighted in the study portrays a clear picture of issues at academic and non-academic departments of Mehran University Jamshoro. (HEIs) Higher Education Institutions must initiate plans for early resolution of issues concerning departments. Presently, universities are running in perspective of ISO-9000-2015 which is pre-requisite and platform where problems are solved.

IX. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of research study, it is recommended that:

A. MACHINERIES AND EQUIPMENT

- University administration and faculty members of departments may strive to acquire

funding that will help to establish the laboratories

- Frequent correspondence with planning and development for work & services
- The labs will be upgraded with equipment and various workshop will be conducted to encourage students to participate

B. INFRASTRUCTURE

- Classroom and offices with proper ventilation
- Insured before every of the semester
- Availability of infrastructure and quality

C. SHORTAGE OF FACULTY

- Improving recruitment and retention strategies
- Improving training strategies, including internal skills development programs, and basing employee development discussions on the learning and development model.

D. ENGINEER JOB MARKET

- Vibrant changes in industrial procedure / process is not meet
- Department assist graduates for job placement and focus in change in syllabus as per industry need.
- To pursue planning of required human resource in the relevant field at PEC & HEC level

E. COMMUNICATION GAP BETWEEN DEPARTMENT AND INDUSTRY

- Conducting seminars and workshops in coordination with industry continuous review of curriculum as per industry needs, increasing attention towards practical knowledge and internship in internships in industry during studies
- Correspondence with industry may be increased.

F. DELAY IN RESPONSE FROM HEC

- Visiting to donor organization
- Pace of compliance and correspondence may be increased
- Industrial advisory board, curriculum update and industrial based case studies

G. LACK OF FINANCIAL SUPPORT FOR EMPLOYEES

- Provide financial support for staff

- You can show your employees how much you care with this additional financial support during the COVID-19 crisis
- Relief payments include reimbursement or pay for personal, family, living or funeral expenses incurred as a result of the disaster

H. DRINKING WATER FACILITY FOR OFFICERS/ OFFICIALS

- Manage safe water delivery system
- Water cooler with filter system must be provide to staff

I. POSSIBLE SHORTAGE OF SPACE DUE TO INCREASING STAFF

- Make more chambers for new employees
- Various functional faculties, departments and units as well as the arrangement of furniture, equipment and work stations within the functional faculties, departments and units to facilitate their work.

J. INFRASTRUCTURE/ EQUIPMENTS

Administration should organize the necessary supplies and the conditions in the area of operation. Some examples of critical equipment include:

- Computers (desktop and laptop)
- Printers
- UPS additional battery packs
- Water, filter and storage
- Containers
- Generator
- Fuel safety and
- Security equipment

J. SYSTEM ARE IN PLACE TO IDENTIFY, PREVENT AND DEAL WITH HAZARDS AT WORK

In order to control workplace hazards and eliminate or reduce the risk, you should take the following steps:

- Identify the hazard by carrying out a workplace risk assessment;
- Determine how employees might be at risk;
- Evaluate the risks;
- Record and review hazards at least annually, or earlier if something changes.

X. RESEARCH LIMITATION

This research limited to Mehran University of Engineering and technology Jamshoro. However, it was restricted to MUET and most research work completed in Jamshoro district. Study mainly focused on risk management in (HEIs) Higher Education Institutions.

XI. FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTION

This study has focused on risk management in higher education n institution at MUET Jamshoro. The scope of this study should be broadened to other universities of Jamshoro.

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Dr. Adnan Pitafi² is an Assistant Professor at department of Mehran Institute of Science, Technology & Development, Mehran University of Engineering & Technology, Jamshoro Sindh, Pakistan.

Dr. Asif Ali Shah² is an Assistant Professor at department of Mehran Institute of Science, Technology & Development, Mehran University of Engineering & Technology, Jamshoro Sindh, Pakistan.

Mehtab Abbasi² is a business student at department of Mehran Institute of Science, Technology & Development, Mehran University of Engineering & Technology, Jamshoro Sindh, Pakistan.

Abdul Ghani Abbasi² is a business student at department of Mehran Institute of Science, Technology & Development, Mehran University of Engineering & Technology, Jamshoro Sindh, Pakistan.

BIOGRAPHIES

Ms. Sonia Memon¹ is a business student at department of Mehran Institute of Science, Technology & Development, Mehran University of Engineering & Technology, Jamshoro Sindh, Pakistan.

Prof. Dr. Abdul Sami Qureshi¹ is Pro-Vice Chancellor of Mehran University of Engineering & Technology Institute Khairpur Mirs Campus Sindh, Pakistan.